

Advanced Environmental Remediation Techniques

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Abstract—Intelligent buildings are responsible for ensuring the indoor air quality for their occupants under normal operation as well as under possibly harmful contaminant events due to accidental or malicious actions. An emerging environmental control application is monitoring the intelligent buildings against the presence of such events, by incorporating various sensing technologies and distributed detection and isolation algorithms. The needed simplicity, the improved scalability and fault tolerance are some of the main reasons for choosing distributed approaches over centralized ones. Hence, the effective partitioning of buildings into smaller sections for contaminant detection and isolation approaches is of great importance. In this paper, we present a heuristic algorithm for partitioning the building into smaller sections. The proposed algorithm is based on matrix clustering techniques and groups the building zones in order to form the different sections while ensuring (i) maximum decoupling between the various sections, (ii) strong connectivity between the zones of a section and (iii) fairness with respect to the number of allocated zones. The partitioning is achieved in near real time, providing the ability of repartitioning and adapting to the dynamic nature of the airflows. The main contribution of this work is the automatic partitioning of the building into sections, which enables the distributed simulation, modeling, analysis and management of the intelligent building while ensuring the effective detection and isolation of contaminants in the building interior.

I. INTRODUCTION

Intelligent buildings are all about ensuring their occupants' comfort, health, productivity and safety. Studies have shown that the majority of indoor air quality (IAQ) problems are caused by various airborne contaminants that are either generated indoors or penetrate into the indoor environment with passive or active airflows [1], [2]. Such contaminant events, could be the result of an accident or a malicious act and require the immediate application of contaminant detection and isolation approaches in order to ensure the safety of the people.

In our previous work [3], we developed a state space method using a multi-zone formulation for the problem of contaminant event monitoring in smart buildings. In this framework, a building consists of a number of zones (e.g. rooms) and, depending on the outside environmental conditions and the locations of doors and windows, there are induced airflows between the various zones due to natural (wind) or forced (fan) ventilation conditions. Thus, the entire building can be viewed

as a system of interacting zones (through the airflows) which can potentially transport air contaminants from one zone of the building to another. In the proposed formulation, the contaminant event source is modeled as a fault in the process, which we would like to detect and isolate (determine the source location). This enables the application of advanced fault diagnosis tools to the problem of contaminant event monitoring in intelligent buildings. Furthermore, in [3] we developed Contaminant Detection and Isolation (CDI) estimator schemes with adaptive thresholds for the detection and isolation of a single contaminant source in the presence of measurement noise and modeling uncertainty.

Centralized contaminant detection and isolation approaches as in [3], however, face the computational complexity problems that emerge as the size of the building increases. In this context, distributed approaches have shown significant benefits over the centralized ones due to (i) the simplicity of smaller subsystems, (ii) improved scalability derived from the easy adaptation to different buildings and (iii) increased reliability due to the lack of a single point of failure [4]. More recently, in [5] we developed a distributed CDI scheme by considering the building as a collection of interconnected subsystems. Buildings offer a natural candidate for such structural partitioning, because they are distributed in space and a particular building zone is only interconnected with a limited number of neighboring zones, mainly through doors and windows. Nonetheless, the success of distributed CDI approaches relies on the proper partitioning of the building into subsystems; note that [5] does not specify exactly how the building partitioning should be performed. Furthermore, for the effective application of the CDI algorithms, the subsystems should be chosen in such a way as to (i) minimize the coupling between the various subsystems in terms of the airflows, (ii) ensure the connectivity of each subsystem so all included zones are connected through at least one airflow and (iii) balance the size between the various subsystems with respect to the number of allocated zones. Most importantly, in a real building setting, the airflows may often change due to variable environmental conditions (temperature, wind direction and

velocity), as well as the opening and closing of doors and windows. Therefore, the partitioning algorithm should also be able to quickly adapt and regroup the building zones under these conditions.

Partitioning techniques have been widely applied in many fields (e.g engineering, machine learning, pattern recognition, image segmentation, etc.). Although, the basic objective of these techniques is the same (the formation of subsystems) for different applications, they can be encountered by different names (decomposition, clustering, grouping, partitioning etc.) depending on the application field. One could distinguish the various techniques in two categories: (i) The techniques that consider the system (the building) as a whole and they try to separate it into subsystems (decomposition and partitioning) and (ii) The techniques that consider the individual parts (the building zones) of the system and try to group them in order to form the subsystems (clustering). Many decomposition techniques have been proposed in the recent decades, however, there is no universal solution that can deal with all decomposition problems, since, the vast majority of approaches are subject to different constraints and objective functions.

For the automatic partitioning of the building application, the most relevant techniques we found in the literature are clustering schemes that incorporate *matrix reordering techniques* which are commonly used in the area of machine component grouping in production flow [6]–[11]. Machine component grouping, arranges machines of different purposes into clusters, to suite production of specific component families, depending on the similarity of operations that are meant to be performed. The objective is to maximize the similarity inside the clusters and minimize it between the clusters. Therefore, machines that execute sequential or similar jobs are clustered together. The dataset consists of a matrix with binary values which indicates the connections between the different machines/components of the system. The goal is to form square blocks of values indicating the clusters as presented in Fig.1, through rearranging the rows and columns of the initial matrix. Each row and its corresponding column are rearranged simultaneously, preserving in this way the initial connectivity between rows and columns. Matrix clustering techniques also ensure the connectivity inside the resulting clusters. Add to this the easy application of size constraints to the formed clusters, where no row is allowed to enter a cluster which has reached a specific size and matrix reordering techniques make a good candidate for building partitioning problems.

In this paper, a heuristic algorithm for the automatic partitioning of buildings is proposed that follows a matrix clustering approach as in [11]. Differently from [11], the proposed algorithm is separated in two phases with new decision logic and individual constraints for each phase, allowing the

partial control of the resulting size and number of subsystems. The algorithm uses the values of airflows between the building zones in order to form the subsystems. Its main objectives are to (i) minimize the *inter-* dependencies (flows) between subsystems (ii) preserve connectivity within each subsystem

Fig. 1. Each shaded block corresponds to a cluster.

and (iii) control the size of the subsystems. Based on the work presented in [5], the modeling uncertainties and the interconnection uncertainties strongly depend on the airflows between the zones; so by minimizing the airflow between the subsystems and controlling their size, the effective application of the distributed contaminant detection and isolation approaches is ensured.

The organization of this paper is as follows: Section II introduces the problem of automatic building partitioning and gives an overview of the problem objective and constraints. Section III presents the two-phase heuristic approach. Section IV provides results for a realistic building case study and Section V concludes the paper.

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION

Consider a n -zone building as a centralized system, where the contaminant dispersion in the indoor environment of the building is described by the following multi-zone model:

$$\Sigma : \dot{x}(t) = (A + \Delta A)x(t) + Q^{-1}Bu(t) + Q^{-1}Gg(t) + w(t) \quad y = Cx(t)$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ represents the concentration of the contaminant in the building zones, while $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the state transition matrix with its elements $A(i,j)$ modeling the changes in contaminant concentration between zone i and zone j , primarily as a result of the air-flows; note that $A(i,j) = 0$ if there is no leakage path connecting zones i and j . The term $\Delta A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ collectively accounts for the presence of modeling uncertainty in the building envelope as a result of the changing wind speed, wind direction and variable leakage openings. The controllable inputs in the form of doors, windows, fans and air handling units are represented by $u \in \mathbb{R}^p$, while $B \in \mathbb{B}^{n \times p}$ is a zone index matrix concerning their location, with $B = \{0,1\}$.

The last term indicates the contaminant sources, represented by $G \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times s}$ and $g \in \mathbb{R}^s$ respectively and $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is a diagonal matrix that holds the volumes of the zones. The outputs of the sensors monitoring Σ are represented by $y \in \mathbb{R}^m$, while $C \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ is a zone index matrix for the sensor locations and $w \in \mathbb{R}^m$ characterizes the additive measurements of noise.

Now consider the same building, decomposed into K interconnected subsystems $\Sigma_I, I \in \{1, \dots, K\}$. The corresponding distributed model is given in [5] as:

$$\Sigma_I: \dot{x}_I(t) = (A_I + \Delta A_I)x_I(t) + Q_I^{-1}B_Iu_I(t) + Q_I^{-1}G_Ig(t) + (H_I + \Delta H_I)z_I(t) y_I = C_Ix_I(t) + w_I(t)$$

where each subsystem consists of n_I zones and $x_I \in \mathbb{R}^{n_I}$ represents the contaminant concentration in zone n_I of subsystem Σ_I . Correspondingly, the controllable inputs in the form of doors, windows, fans and air handling units represented by $u_I \in \mathbb{R}^{p_I}$, the local measured output by $y_I \in \mathbb{R}^{m_I}$ and the vector of interconnection variables by $z_I \in \mathbb{R}^l$. The term $g_I \in \mathbb{R}$ represents the local contaminant source, $G_I \in \mathbb{R}^{n_I}$ represents the location zone of the contaminant source and $w_I \in \mathbb{R}^{m_I}$ corresponds to the local noise vector. Terms, $A_I, \Delta A_I, B_I, Q_I, G_I$ and C_I are sub-matrices of the appropriate dimensions of the corresponding matrices of the centralized system Σ . Finally, H_I are sub-matrices of A and ΔH_I are sub-matrices of ΔA_I that account for the interconnection uncertainties related to the interconnection variables z_I , which are calculated as the difference of the real and the nominal values of the air flow.

The objective of this work is to provide an automatic algorithm for forming the subsystems Σ_I while minimizing the flows that traverse between them; hence minimizing the interconnection effects $(H_I + \Delta H_I)$. Since, H and ΔH_I are sub-matrices of A and ΔA_I respectively which include all the values that are related to flows traversing between two subsystems, therefore the problem is reduced to the formation of blocks in the state transition matrix A . By reducing the interconnection uncertainty, the residual bounds are also reduced leading to tighter adaptive thresholds for both the contaminant detector and isolator schemes described in [5]. Therefore, the time delay for contaminant detection and isolation is reduced and the overall performance of the approach is also increased. Moreover, controlling the size of the blocks, keeps the computational effort required under control. Note that the computational complexity of the contaminant detection and isolation schemes increases with the number of involved zones. In fact, when large buildings are considered, the calculation of the adaptive thresholds may become a formidable task.

In summary, starting with the state transition matrix A of a building system Σ , the objective of the proposed algorithm is to form blocks of values inside A corresponding to the building subsystems Σ_I such as to: a) minimize the airflows between them b) control their size and c) ensure their connectivity.

In the sequel, $f: N \rightarrow K$, where $N = \{0, \dots, n-1\}, K = \{1, \dots, k\}$, is a function that gives the index of the block which includes row $i \in N$, n is the total number of row/columns of matrix A and K indicates the total number of blocks. Also, M_k is a set corresponding to the k^{th} block and includes all the indices of the rows that are included in the k^{th} block. The notation $|M_k|$ is used to indicate the size of the k^{th}

block, while \bar{M} and \underline{M} are the maximum and minimum size constraints which are common for all the blocks. Finally, the sum of values that are not included in any block is defined as the *partitioning cost*. Note that, one of the objectives of our partitioning solution is to reduce this cost as much as possible.

1) *Building simulation example:* For demonstrating the operation of the algorithm, we use a building simulation example created in CONTAM [12], a multizone airflow and contaminant transport analysis software. For the investigated

Fig. 2. Airflow simulation example in CONTAM software.

-451.178					133.922	
	-610.096					
		-1083.51	96.6373			874.886
			-193.275	80.0575		
				-80.0575		
	305.048	416.612			-721.659	
						-1974.98

Fig. 3. State transition matrix A with the airflow values between the zones.

scenario, we assume natural ventilation conditions with the wind blowing from the north-east while all the leakage paths (doors and windows) are in the fully open position. The building layout and the corresponding A matrix for the particular scenario are portrayed in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 respectively. The green lines in Fig. 2 represent the airflows

(magnitude and direction) at the various leakage paths of the building while the airflow magnitudes are also included in the corresponding positions of the A matrix in Fig. 3. For example, if $A(i,j) \neq 0$ it means that the i^{th} zone has a leakage connection with the j^{th} zone with an airflow value indicated by the value of the cell $A(i,j), i, j \in \mathbb{N}$. Note that the diagonal elements of the A matrix represent the sum of incoming flows in each zone. Since they are not needed for partitioning the building, in the sequel they will be set to zero.

III. BUILDING PARTITIONING ALGORITHM

The heuristic algorithm consists of two phases. In the first phase, *Dividing*, the matrix is separated into blocks following a constraint on the maximum number of rows inside a block. In the second phase, *Regrouping*, the smaller blocks are merged with the bigger ones by applying the second constraint on the minimum number of rows allowed inside a block. Below we provide more details on each of the phases.

A. Phase 1: Dividing

The Dividing phase is responsible of constructing groups of values, indicating the blocks, while satisfying a maximum block size constraint. Its decisions are based on the differences between the values that are inside the formed blocks and those left outside.

At the beginning of the Dividing phase, each row of the matrix is separated and a block for each one (referred to as singleton block) is formed (line 3 of Phase 1). For example, if the matrix dimensions are $n \times n$, then $k = n$ singleton blocks are formed at the beginning where each block holds one of the rows. Then, a series of merges between the matrix rows

Phase 1 : Dividing

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1:  $i, j \in \mathbb{N}$ 
2: Set the maximum subsystem size  $M$ 
3: for all rows  $i$  do Generate singleton block  $M_{f(i)}$  end for
4: Set  $Improved \leftarrow False$ 
5: Set  $Visited = \{\emptyset\}$ 
6: for all rows  $i$  do
7:   for all rows  $j$  do
8:     if  $(A(i,j) > 0 \ \&\& \ f(i) \neq f(j) \ \&\& \ (i,j) \notin Visited)$ 
9:        $Visited = Visited \cup (i,j)$ 
10:       $S = \sum_{l_1 \in M_{f(i)} \ l_2 \in M_{f(j)}} A(l_1, l_2)$ 
11:      Let  $S_{i,j}$  denote the sum of values of blocks
12:       $M_{f(i)}$  and  $M_{f(j)}$  after moving row  $i$  to block  $M_{f(j)}$ 
13:      If  $S_{i,j} > S_{j,i}$  then

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14:      If  $|M_{f(j)}| < M$  then 15:      Move row
i to block  $M_{f(j)}$ 
16: else Replace the row from  $M_{f(j)}$  with row  $i$  that maximizes  $S$ 
17:       end if
18:     end if
19:   If  $S_{j,i} > S_{i,j}$  then
20:     If  $|M_{f(i)}| < M$  then 21:     Move row
j to block  $M_{f(i)}$ 
22: else Replace the row from  $M_{f(i)}$  with row  $j$  that maximizes  $S$ 
23:       end if
24:     end if
25:   if  $S$  is increased then
26:     Set  $Improved \leftarrow True$ 
27:   else 28:   If  $S_{j,i} = S_{i,j}$  then
29:     Move row from the bigger block to the smaller
30:     end if
31:   end if 32: end if
33:   end for
34: end for
35: if  $Improved = False$  then
36:   End of the Dividing phase
37: else
38:   go to Line 4
39: end if

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are performed, in order to maximize the values inside each block and minimize the remaining ones. Note that, while n is constant, k changes during the execution of the algorithm. For each merger to be executed, it first needs to inspect whether by merging two rows together, a better block is formed with respect to its included values. With each row rearrangement the corresponding column is rearranged simultaneously so as to preserve the initial row-column data connections.

This process follows a greedy approach where instead of finding the best possible move to be executed at each step, it

				80.0575			
		96.6373					874.886
	305.048		416.612				
					133.922		

Fig. 4. Screenshot during the execution of the Dividing phase. $M=3$, rows $i=3$ and $j=4$ are processed.

				80.0575			
		96.6373					874.886
305.048		416.612					
					133.922		

Fig. 5. Screenshot during the execution of the Dividing phase. $M=3$, rows $i=2$ and $j=6$ are candidates to be moved.

moves the first two rows together if a lower partitioning cost is achieved. Apart from the aforementioned row moving policy, it also prohibits a row from entering a block that has reached its maximum size constraint. A row swapping procedure is also possible when a block reaches its size limit. Compared to the approach in [11], the proposed approach differs in the decision logic that determines which row and where it should be moved. The possibility of reaching optimality increases considerably with the swapping procedure. Furthermore, the swapping capabilities render the heuristic capable of enforcing a maximum block size constraint without affecting the quality of the result.

On each step of the Dividing phase, two rows (row i and row j) from different blocks are processed. Consider the example of Fig. 4 which represents a snapshot of the algorithm after a number of steps where 2 non-singleton blocks have been formed and indicated by the shaded areas providing a total of 5 blocks: $M_1 = \{1\}, M_2 = \{3,2\}, M_3 = \{4\}, M_4 = \{5,0\}, M_5 = \{6\}$ (where $M_{f(3)} = M_{f(2)} = M_2$ and $M_{f(5)} = M_{f(0)} = M_4$). The rows have been randomly assigned a number at the beginning. Rows $i=3$ and $j=4$ are currently processed which are connected through an airflow indicated by $A(3,4) = 80.0575$. Rows 3 and 4 are included in blocks $M_{f(3)} = M_2$ and $M_{f(4)} = M_3$ respectively.

Since row 4 is in a singleton block and a connection with row 3 exists then row 4 is moved in the block $M_{f(3)} = M_2$ providing the matrix presented in Fig. 5. After a few iterations without any matrix changes rows $i=2$ and $j=6$ are processed. Since there exist a connection with row 2 then by inserting row 6 in the $M_{f(2)}$ block, the sum of values inside the block will increase. However, since the maximum block size

limit is set to $M=3$, then block $M_{f(2)}$ has reached its size limit. Therefore, because a value in block $M_{f(2)}$ exists that is smaller than the value $A(2,6)$ and corresponds to element $A(3,4)$ then row 6 is swapped with row 4 as appears in Fig.6.

The resulting matrix of the 'Dividing' phase appears in Fig.7 which shows that there have been formed 3 blocks. One singleton and two blocks of 3 rows each. As expected, one row (i.e row 4) is left in a singleton block since two non-

	80.0575						
		96.6373		874.886			
	305.048		416.612				
						133.922	

Fig. 6. Result of the swapping of rows $i=4$ and $j=6$ with $M=3$.

	80.0575						
		96.6373		874.886			
			416.612				
					133.922		305.048

Fig. 7. Matrix resulting from the Dividing phase.

singleton blocks have resulted and the maximum block size is set to $M=3$.

Overall, the Dividing phase manages to form the blocks of values by rearranging the rows according to the maximum block size and ensures that the values inside the formed blocks are as big as possible. However, since the maximum size constraint remains constant and the number of blocks is not known *a priori*, some rows might not be included in any block. The solution to this problem, is given by the Regrouping phase which is responsible for handling those rows.

B. Phase 2: Regrouping

The Regrouping phase is where the blocks are finalized and hence is where the subsystems for the CDI method are determined. It incorporates a minimum block size constraint. All blocks that do not satisfy it are merged with other existing blocks. Note that it can negate the maximum subsystem size

constraint of the Dividing phase, however, it is essential since the final solution can not include any singleton blocks.

From the resulting matrix of the 'Dividing' phase in Fig. 7, it is obvious that, row 4 needs to be included in one of the already established bigger blocks in order for the result to be valid. A block with one row and hence a subsystem with one zone would not be beneficial nor practical for the CDI method. Therefore, using the minimum block size constraint, the blocks or individual rows that need to be merged with bigger blocks are identified. Then, the decision as to which block will be merged with the smaller blocks is taken based on which merger results in the best overall solution. In other words, small blocks are merged with the blocks for which the sum of values connecting them is the largest. The example presented in Fig. 7 shows that row 4 is only connected with row 3. Therefore, row 4 is merged with the block of row 3, resulting in a two block solution. The resulting building partitioning appears in Fig. 8.

It is clear, that the role of the Regrouping phase is crucial in order to reach valid results. Due to the size limitations that are enforced to the blocks in the Dividing phase, its solution may not be valid for use in the CDI method. Hence, by incorporating a minimum block size constraint in the

Fig. 8. The corresponding building partitioning based on the algorithm's solution.

Phase 2 : Regrouping phase

- 1: Set Minimum Zone Size \underline{M}
- 2: while *Blocks with size < \underline{M} exist* do
- 3: for all *Blocks $M_i, i \in K$ with size < \underline{M}* do
- 4: for all *Connected blocks $M_j, j \in K$* do
- 5: Merge block M_i with block M_j which
- 6: maximizes the sum of values inside the blocks
- 7: end for
- 8: end for
- 9: end while

Regrouping phase, the blocks for the CDI method are finalized. Additionally, there is the possibility of controlling the resulting number of blocks by inducing extra limitations in the Dividing phase and repeatedly merging the blocks until those limitations are met.

C. Partitioning Algorithm Constraints

As far as the composition of the resulting subsystems is concerned, the initial matrix A ordering can affect the results due to the row processing sequence. Not only the resulting partitioning cost but also, the resulting number of subsystems may vary significantly, for different initializations. Also, the minimum subsystem size is always ensured; however this is not the case for the maximum subsystem size since it may be negated by the Regrouping phase. Consequently, the algorithm is executed for different maximum and minimum constraints and different initial matrix orderings, keeping only the best result for every different number of subsystems. In this way, a set of solutions is obtained for a range of resulting subsystem numbers.

Subsystem's connectivity is also one of the algorithm's main restrictions. The row moving policy of the heuristic approach, where two rows are merged in the same block if and only if an airflow exists between them, follows the connectivity restrictions. On the other hand, invalid solutions may be reached due to the swapping procedure, but are highly unlikely. Even though invalid solutions are not common, each result is evaluated at the end of the algorithm using a breadth first search separately in each subsystem and is discarded if not all zones are reachable within that subsystem. Since invalid solutions are not common, testing for connectivity in every step of the algorithm was not included to avoid increasing the computational complexity.

Fig. 9. Comparison of results obtained from the exhaustive and proposed heuristic method.

IV. RESULTS

The heuristic algorithm was tested on the Holmes¹ house. The matrix of flows that has been used was constructed using the CONTAM software. The Holmes house consists of 14 zones and a total of 12 flows. The optimal results in terms of minimizing the decomposition cost for 3-5 resulting blocks have been derived through an exhaustive search using a brute force approach by limiting the minimum block size to

$\underline{M} = 2$ and the maximum block size to $M = 5$. The heuristic algorithm was executed for all combinations of values for minimum block size $\underline{M} = 2, 3, 4$ and maximum block size

$M = 3, 4, 5, 6$. Note that the resulting number of blocks is not predetermined. Thus, the best solution for each individual resulting number of blocks was kept and the other solutions were discarded. The results are presented in Fig. 9.

The results indicate that the heuristic performs very good in all the three resulting numbers of blocks and for the particular house achieves optimal results. Also, it achieved these results by running a relatively small combination of minimum and maximum block sizes. Since the heuristic is not testing all possible solutions exhaustively, it cannot guarantee its results will be optimal. Furthermore, a close analysis of the composition of the formed blocks indicates that the heuristic tends to provide blocks of relatively the same size. This is a consequence of the decision making logic of the heuristic which is one of the objectives for the CDI methodology. Moreover, it appears capable of providing the CDI method with valid subsystems that follow the size and connectivity constraints.

V. CONCLUSION

Contaminant event detection and isolation in multi-zone intelligent buildings is responsible for ensuring the occupants health, productivity and safety. Successful deployment of such distributed approaches, require a method for dividing the building into subsystems. In order to form the subsystems for the distributed CDI method presented in [5], in this paper

¹Refers to a low-rise residential house model used by J.D. Holmes and then scaled up for Simulating Airflow and Contaminant Transport in and around Buildings [13].

we have developed a heuristic algorithm that uses as input the state transition matrix of the CDI approach (which holds the airflows that connect the zones of the buildings) and using matrix reordering techniques is able to form blocks of values indicating the subsystems. The algorithm is able to minimize the subsystem interdependencies and preserve the initial connectivity while maintaining size constraints, which are all essential for increasing the performance of the CDI approach. In particular, controlling the results in terms of subsystem size can reduce computational complexity and improve the performance of the contaminant detection and isolation method.

Future challenges include testing the heuristic algorithm and evaluating its results in large-scale real buildings, incorporating the heuristic algorithm in the CDI approach and considering its real-time implementation.

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